

Security analysis and recommendations: Web application and systems vulnerabilities

Yohannes Tadesse, Ph.D.

College of Business and Management, Metrostate University, St. Paul

Department of Computer Science and Cybersecurity, Metrostate University, St. Paul

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Abstract

Handling sensitive data is the most crucial part of an organization's business operation. There have been incidents where companies have been sued for liabilities and experienced bankruptcy for mishandling sensitive data and being unable to secure application and network systems. Thus, organizations are prompted to implement the best procedures or routines for storing sensitive data in a highly secure environment. Hence, the standard practices of requirements to exert integrity on sensitive data, organizations enforce risk management processes to preserve and ensure secure data flows and information exchanges. This paper will explore and review some of the countermeasures and models that assist organizations in identifying web-based application and systems vulnerabilities and provide solutions to mitigate security risks within the information systems architecture.

Keywords: business operation; security analysis; risk assessment; application systems vulnerabilities; security policies

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The risk management process provides policies and procedures to establish strategies for analyzing, mitigating, and communicating the importance of risks in all business processes. Risk occurrence varies among business processes, and the effect can be measured in terms of likelihood and consequence. Therefore, understanding the key areas of risk will increase our ability to eliminate or minimize the adverse threats that are highly possible within an organization's business processes (Herrmann, P. & Herrmann, G., 2006).

Risk assessment is an overall process of risk analysis and risk evaluation. It is utilized to identify, assess, and prioritize risks, ensuring that the causes and effects of a risk are accurately established. Liu, Kuhn, and Rossman (2009) emphasize that risk "uses available threat, vulnerability, process, and asset information to identify threats and estimate the associated risk, and evaluation compares this estimate against a set of criteria to determine the risk's significance and impact" (p. 57).

Despite the risk prevention strategies, risks are generally categorized as high, medium, and low. Risk analysis is a method to assess the impact of potential risks that may affect various entities within the organization. Risk analysis measures the likelihood of all potential risks that impact tasks and activities during the project life cycle. Moreover, risk analysis aims to separate the foreseeable and unforeseeable, providing data to assist in evaluation and risk management. Risks are analyzed in two specific methods: qualitative analysis to describe the magnitude and potential consequences, and quantitative analysis, in which numerical values are employed to determine the likelihood of consequences of risks from several collected data sources (Liu, Kuhn, & Rossman, 2009).

The crucial strategy of risk management processes is to mitigate and eliminate potential risk factors. Thus, this paper provides a security analysis to determine and identify potential vulnerabilities and security holes that could generate a cascading effect on business performance and sustainability. The security analysis employs a security assessment tool to conduct relevant analytical procedures and generate substantive information about the security status within the architecture.

Web-based Application Analysis

The web-based application analysis aims to determine system vulnerabilities and how our systems are protected from potential threats. This process scrutinizes the level of security and can identify potential security holes that are crucial to the organization's business sustainability. In addition, the analysis procedure will induce greater security awareness and comprehensive mitigation procedures for risk management processes, thereby ensuring and strengthening the organization's systems' security objectives. The plan will evaluate the organization's internal network access controls specific to the application and file-sharing processes.

As application and systems vulnerabilities face growing security threats, an organization's highest priority is to devise an effective security plan or evaluate its existing security guidelines to ensure business continuity. This plan aims to thoroughly understand the security requirements essential to preserve the organization's business objectives, which incorporate confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data and information within the systems. Moreover, the plan will resolve the following security requirements that are essential to the organization's business operations:

1. The organization's confidential information will be secured and protected based on the access privileges and roles;

2. The organization's systems must be protected against potential risks that increase vulnerabilities and breaches of confidential information and data.
3. Organizations' authorization and authentication mechanisms must efficiently protect network systems and applications from unauthorized access.

Vulnerabilities identification and assessment

Because of the criticality of risks, security implementation has been given the highest priority within organizations where data privileges and rights are restricted through strategic plans and access control implementation mechanisms. Thus, organizations are devising strategies that recommend and implement standards and protocols to address identified vulnerabilities.

Balzarotti, Cova, Felmetzger, and Vigna (2007) explain dataflow and workflow attacks, which impact web-based applications. Balzarotti et al. (2007) developed multi-module analysis methodologies to expand the identification of vulnerabilities that provide the broader aspect of security requirements within the application process. The authors modeled based on the intended workflow and extended state analysis to tackle complex web application vulnerabilities. This multi-module analysis is specifically developed to provide a substantial advantage in analyzing web-based applications through static code analysis to provide solutions to false positive identifications.

Thus, this action plan prompts specific areas in the organization's internal application and systems security requirements to meet expectations on securing and protecting the network environment. The following security vulnerabilities are identified as the potential target areas that the internal application systems architecture could incur for security assessment and analysis routine:

1. Identify potential vulnerabilities in access control mechanisms, such as authorization and authentication privileges, related to internal network system applications.
2. To assess the level of security based on implemented security roles where applications and systems confront potential threats.
3. During the evaluation process, assess the organization's current security standards and guidelines for the analyzed information.

Chapman and Hilton (2004) also examine the use of multi-level security analysis, providing an information flow model that renders “whole-program analysis, determining subprogram integrity level once all invocations ... [and] partial-program analysis, annotating each critical subprogram declaration with its integrity level and checking at declaration and each invocation that the maximum integrity level is not violated” (p. 44). Chapman and Hilton introduced information flow analysis, which employs SPARK Ada and Examiner tools to provide effective solutions for critical application vulnerabilities. This model offers multi-level security analysis, which answers identified gaps in the information flow analysis technique.

Web application vulnerabilities are increasingly raising significant concerns within the business community that offers dynamic web pages and interactive experiences with consumers. For instance, SQL injection, cross-site scripting, and other multi-module attacks let hackers exploit trusted websites, making them vulnerable to malicious attacks that provide information and circumvent the secure realm of data integrity (Balzarotti et al., 2007).

Additionally, Lam, Martin, Livshits, and Whaley (2008) identified SQL injection and Cross-site scripting (XSS) as common security threats that web-based applications encounter

during software development. Thus, the authors suggest solutions to mitigate these vulnerabilities and introduce static context-sensitive methods, which determine information flow tracking and model checking analysis. The authors expound on effective methodologies that identify security vulnerabilities in web applications through “basic information flow, context-sensitive pointer alias analysis, dynamic monitoring, and modeling checking” (Lam et al., 2008, p. 11).

As risks and vulnerabilities become prevalent, third-party management groups will also increase in providing and proposing solutions to organizations valuing security issues as the primary concern in their business operations. The reliability and accountability of information impose software innovations that protect and secure the integrity of data based on network configuration and analysis, which provides the overall security evaluative measure. Evaluative measures include automated security mechanisms that support organizational security policies that need “secure systems to respond to changing conditions, [which] implies the support for dynamic policies” (Levin, Irvine, Weissman, and Nguyen, 2007, p. 42) to realize accountability and reliability.

Application of a tool to conduct the analysis

Although Microsoft Baseline Security Analyzer (MBSA) provides comprehensive but frequently recognized security holes, the tool identifies vulnerabilities based on the configured requirements and reports expected results. The application conducts specific analysis and criteria to aggregate security vulnerabilities such as authentication/authorization, system upgrades, patches, potential external security threats, and implications.

One risk protection mechanism is for organizations to maintain adequate risk management policies, while security risks should be evaluated and analyzed frequently. Security

awareness and integrated security policies and procedures are essential to protect against security breaches. Most importantly, organizations must implement a systems security analysis program to raise awareness, become proactive, and utilize countermeasures based on the analysis report gathered from provisioned security analysis procedures.

Liu, Holt, and Cheng (2007) elaborate on the criticality of a vulnerability assessment program that provides a comprehensive advantage to information, data integrity, and confidentiality. As the enterprise business environment grows, the need for effective security implementation programs becomes relevant and critical. Liu et al. (2007) describe “a practical and repeatable methodology to manage the vulnerability assessment program (VAP) and a set of vulnerability detection and remediation practices to effectively implement and maintain a VAP life cycle” (p. 36). Vulnerability assessment programs incorporate network, host, application, and alternate ingress scanning methods within enterprise architecture to ensure and offer broader security mechanisms.

Although risk assessment tools are developed to determine applications and systems vulnerabilities, it is also possible to override the purpose of security futures. Primarily, the focus is on the impact of security analyzers that can create weaknesses in security issues where tools work against administrators and facilitate hackers’ intentions, which automated security analysis tools may pose potential threats and vulnerabilities. Thus, Furnell, Chiliarhaki, and Dowland (2001) indicate that “several tools and pre-written attacks (often referred to as exploit programs) have been released by hacker community itself, providing not only the means to identify a vulnerability automatically but also to take advantage of it, to the detriment of the target system” (p. 93).

Analysis Results

The analysis result covers two main categories, which include the application and the system (JBoss web application server) implementation, in which security requirements have been analyzed within the internal information systems architecture. The authentication/authorization process within the internal application is identified as the primary and critical security issues reported. Severity and vulnerability ratings are determined based on the identified risks. As Furnell, Chillarchaki, and Dowland (2001) explain, the extensive benefit of software innovation provides “complex functionalities” (p. 100), which assist administrators in identifying the criticality of vulnerabilities and insights to adapt countermeasures.

Applications and web servers are equally vulnerable to security threats, and organizations are investing in and implementing the best technologies to protect systems critical to businesses’ availability. Organizations must develop standards or guidelines to implement more substantial security criteria or procedures for access controls, such as authentication and authorization mechanisms. Web servers such as JBoss or Apache containers provide multiple configuration mechanisms and technical aspects to ensure security for enterprise services.

Strengths and weaknesses of the system and application

Although organizations enforce rigorous security policies and standards, web-based application authentication mechanisms have notable security weaknesses. These weaknesses could extend security problems that cause more significant damage to the entire network system. Some application vulnerabilities lack input validation checks that protect against malicious code injections, creating system failures that impact system performance. Thus, some relevant recommendations are essential to mitigate the identified security vulnerabilities in the information security implementation program.

The complexity of security analysis and the expert that supports the processes maintain and provide in-depth security mechanisms to ensure adequate security implementation. Thus, developing a framework is essential and assists network security in implementing and modifying security requirements based on object-oriented business processes. Hermann, P. and Hermann, G. (2006) incorporated an analysis tool to maintain a graphical representation to determine the seriousness of security concerns identified during the assessment process. The graphical representation provides cost and countermeasure analysis related to the business process with sufficient security protection.

The strengths and weaknesses of web application security define the status of availability and reliability of presentation that employs counter-measures against internal or external threats where information flow, static, and dynamic analysis are integral to determine the security status (Lam, Martin, Livshits, & Whaley, 2008).

Recommendation

The lack of network intrusion detection tools jeopardizes and affects the confidentiality and integrity of information available within the infrastructure. The advantage of employing an intrusion detection mechanism is that it can provide the ability to identify anomalous activities. The Federal Information Security Management Act of 2002 (FISMA) imposes security control mechanisms that organizations must consider best security enforcement within the IT resources. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) proposes security control and mechanisms that organizations could employ based on their organization's information security standards (Chuvakin, 2007). For instance, applying intrusion-detection tools to system-wide protection reinforces standard protocols. In the meantime, automated tools should be employed to support near-real-time analysis of events to detect system-level attacks. This includes

automation to integrate intrusion-detection tools into access control and follow control mechanisms for rapid response to threats and attacks by enabling stringent security procedures.

In addition, critical and confidential data must be encrypted in two ways (data in transaction and data at rest) to avoid any form of vulnerability. Thus, robust authentication and authorization mechanisms instill confidence essential for safeguarding confidential and private information rather than facing privacy breaches. Cryptography methodologies (public-key, symmetric-key, identity-based, etc.) generally verify the security protocol by providing different algorithmic computations. These algorithms impart complex computations by demonstrating the merit of specific areas of cryptographic techniques. For instance, in 1984, Shamir introduced an Identity-based cryptosystem, which maintains a favorable choice in a distributed network environment to provide secure, reliable, and delay-tolerant communication issues (Asokan et al., 2007, p. 52).

Liu, Kuhn, and Rossman (2009) emphasize that insecure information technology processes contribute to cascading effects on the organizations' business sustainability. Thus, practical risk assessment methodologies to identify, analyze, and prioritize security risks are crucial to mitigate risks and develop strategies. Moreover, risk assessments can also be achieved with quantitative and/or qualitative approaches to establish automated or manual assessment methodologies. However, security issues that pose challenges yet serve as beneficial actions regarding the practical use of effective security assessment methods also highlight the lack of demonstrated business value and benefit, impractical measures to address risks, tedious and time-consuming processes, and a shortage of skilled systems security personnel (Liu et al., 2009).

Conclusion

As the organization's business objectives and services continue to grow, technological innovations also provide remarkable advantages for achieving processes more effectively and reliably. The department acknowledges that the importance of acquiring effective and strong security implementation cannot be compromised. Meanwhile, security assessments should be performed constantly to identify security risks, as threats are becoming complex and continuously changing. Adequate information security is critical and integral to ensuring confidentiality and integrity throughout the business process.

Although IT security strategy is rigorous, continuous updates and strategic measures are imperative to standardize an organization's security implementation plans. Ameri (2004) expounds that prevention is a very arduous task that provides secure implementation plans to mitigate unpredictable security breaches that usually occur and infiltrate to cause colossal damage to the infrastructure. Thus, to be one step ahead of the IT risk factors, organizations must be vigilant and ascertain risk management processes as the primary objectives of the business operation.

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